

Synthesis and biological activity of some *N*-aryl-4-(5-methyl-[1,3,4]-oxadiazolin-2-one-3-yl) substituted benzamides from 3-(4-carboxy)phenylsydnone

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Manuscript received 11 April 2005, revised 8 May 2006, accepted 31 July 2006

Abstract : The title compounds *N*-aryl-4-(5-methyl-[1,3,4]-oxadiazolin-2-one-3-yl) substituted benzamides (5a-h) were synthesized from 3-(4-carboxy)phenylsydnone (1) by using one-pot ring conversion reaction of sydnone to 1,3,4-oxadiazolin-2-one. Preliminary antimicrobial screening of these compounds exhibited higher activity for some of them as compared to the reference drugs used.

Keywords : Phenylsydnone, heterocycles, biological activity.

Sydneses are one of the few heterocycles, which have gained importance as synthons as they readily undergo one-pot ring transformation to various heterocycles by 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition¹. The ease of formation of these heterocycles from sydneses increases the synthetic utility of this ring conversion, as only few such oxadiazolinones obtained by difficulty and in very low yield, starting from phenyl hydrazine have been reported in the literature². In continuation of our earlier work³, in the present communication we have reported the preparation of some of the so far unknown benzamide derivatives of oxadiazolinones. Benzamide derivatives that are possible metabolites of benzoxazoles exhibit various types of biological properties such as anthelmintic, antihistaminic and antimicrobial activities⁴.

Results and discussion

In the present investigation we have prepared the title compounds using one-pot ring conversion reaction of 3-(4-carboxy)phenylsydnone⁵ (1). We planned to synthesize the title compound by two different methods. In the first method we thought of preparing the acid chloride of 3-(4-carboxy)phenylsydnone (1) followed by condensation reaction with aromatic amines in order to get the benzamides, which on further one-pot ring conversion with bromine in acetic anhydride⁶ would yield the title compounds (5a-h). However, this method was not successful because the HCl liberated during the reaction cleaved the sydnone ring and the product could not be isolated.

In an alternate method 3-(4-carboxy)phenylsydnone

(1) was first converted to the 3-(4-carboxy)phenyl-5-methyl-[1,3,4]-oxadiazolin-2-one (3) by one-pot ring conversion reaction with bromine in acetic anhydride, which on further reaction with thionyl chloride yielded the corresponding acid chloride - 4-(5-methyl-[1,3,4]-oxadiazolin-2-one-3-yl) benzoyl chloride (4) which on reaction with aromatic amines in presence of triethyl amine yielded the desired *N*-aryl-4-(5-methyl-[1,3,4]-oxadiazolin-2-one-3-yl) benzamides (5a-h) (Scheme 1). All the newly synthesized compounds were characterized by their physical and spectral data. The IR of compound 3 showed the

5a, R = H; 5b, R = 4-Br; 5c, R = 2-CH₃, 5d, R = 4-CH₃;
5e, R = 2-Cl; 5f, R = 4-Cl; 5g, R = 2-OCH₃; 5h, R = 2-OCH₃

Scheme 1

absence of sharp sydnone ν_{CH} band at 3125 cm^{-1} and shift in the carbonyl frequency of sydnone from $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ 1739 to 1782 cm^{-1} , and also the absence of the $^1\text{H NMR}$ signal for sydnone ring proton, which is an indication for the ring transformation of sydnone to oxadiazolinone. Compound **4** in its IR spectrum showed the absence of broad band at 3423 cm^{-1} for $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ and appearance of two sharp bands at 1782 and 1739 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ of acid chloride and oxadiazolinone ring. The IR spectra of compounds **5a-h** showed sharp band at 3366 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$. The $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ of oxadiazolinone and amide appeared as sharp bands at 1769 and 1665 cm^{-1} respectively. A typical $^1\text{H NMR}$ spectrum of **5a-h** showed signals at δ 2.39 (3H, s, CH_3), 7.16–8.11 for aromatic protons and a D_2O exchangeable NH proton at 10.21.

Biological activity :

The preliminary antimicrobial testing has been carried out by cup-plate method. The antimicrobial activity was done against two pathogenic bacteria – *Escherichia coli* (Gram –ve) and *Micrococcus luteus* (Gram +ve) and *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium notatum* as the fungal strains. The reference drugs used were Norfloxacin and Griseofulvin respectively. The samples and the reference drugs were screened at $50\text{ }\mu\text{g}/0.1\text{ ml}$ DMSO under identical conditions and the zone of inhibition was measured in mm. Compounds **5e** and **5f** with chlorine substitution on the phenyl ring showed considerable activity only against *E. coli*. Whereas compound **5g** (4- OCH_3) showed antifungal activity almost equal to that of the reference drug only against *A. niger*. While rest of the compounds showed only weak to moderate activity against all the

microbes. The detailed results are shown in Table 1.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary tube and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on Nicolet-Impact 410 FT-IR spectrophotometer as KBr pellets. $^1\text{H NMR}$ and ^{13}C spectra were recorded on Bruker 300 MHz FT-NMR spectrometer in $\text{CDCl}_3/\text{DMSO}-d_6$ with TMS as an internal standard. Purity of the compounds was checked by TLC on silica gel plate.

Preparation of 3-(4-carboxy)phenyl-5-methyl-[1,3,4]-oxadiazolin-2-one (3) :

By the literature method⁶: yield 90%, m.p. $124\text{--}126^\circ$ (Found : C, 54.15; H, 3.28; N, 12.52. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$: C, 54.54; H, 3.63; N, 12.72%); ν_{max} $3200\text{--}2800$ (br, OH), 1754 cm^{-1} (oxadiazolinone C=O); δ (DMSO- d_6) 2.45 (3H, s, CH_3), 7.65 (2H, d, ArH, J 8.0 Hz), 7.83 (2H, d, ArH, J 8.0 Hz).

Preparation of 4-(5-methyl-[1,3,4]-oxadiazolin-2-one-3-yl) benzoyl chloride (4) :

A mixture of 3-(4-carboxy)phenyl-5-methyl-[1,3,4]-oxadiazolin-2-one (**3**) (5 g) and thionyl chloride (10 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for 3 h. The excess of thionyl chloride was removed under reduced pressure and the solid separated was washed with pet-ether. The crude acid chloride thus obtained was sufficiently pure for the next step, (85%), m.p. $178\text{--}180^\circ$ (Found : C, 50.02; H, 2.85; N, 11.66. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_3$: C, 50.20; H, 2.92; N, 11.71%); ν_{max} 1754 (oxadiazolinone C=O), 1739 cm^{-1} (acid chloride C=O); δ (CDCl_3) 2.39 (3H, s, CH_3), 7.40 (2H, d, ArH, J 8.6 Hz), 7.92 (2H, d, ArH, J 8.6 Hz).

Table 1. Antimicrobial activity of compounds **5a-h**

Compd.	R	Antibacterial activity		Antifungal activity	
		Zone of inhibition (mm)		Zone of inhibition (mm)	
		<i>E. coli</i>	<i>M. luteus</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>P. notatum</i>
5a	H	16	11	10	10
5b	4-Br	24	11	15	11
5c	2- CH_3	19	10	12	–
5d	4- CH_3	24	11	14	13
5e	2-Cl	28	13	13	10
5f	4-Cl	27	14	17	11
5g	2- OCH_3	21	11	18	12
5h	4- OCH_3	17	10	17	10
Norfloxacin		31	15	–	–
Griseofulvin		–	–	18	15

Preparation of N-aryl-4-(5-methyl-[1,3,4]-oxadiazolin-2-one-3-yl) substituted benzamides (5a-h) :

A solution of acid chloride (4) (0.01 m, 2.3 g) in dry acetone was added dropwise to a stirred solution of aromatic amine (0.01 m) in dry acetone in the presence of triethyl amine (2 ml) at 0–5 °C and stirred for 6 h. The residue obtained after removal of excess solvent was suspended in water and neutralized with 10% sodium carbonate solution, the solid separated was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol **5a** (71%), m.p. 138–140° (Found : C, 64.62; H, 4.05; N, 14.16. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₃N₃O₃ : C, 65.08; H, 4.40; N, 14.23%); ν_{\max} 3366 (NH), 1754 (oxadiazolinone C=O), 1667 cm⁻¹ (amide C=O); δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 2.45 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.11–7.40 (5H, m, ArH), 7.65 (2H, d, ArH, *J* 8.0 Hz), 7.83 (2H, d, ArH, *J* 8.0 Hz), 10.12 (1H, s, NH, D₂O exchanged). **5b** (75%), m.p. 151–154° (Found : C, 51.09; H, 2.85; N, 10.95. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₂BrN₃O₃ : C, 51.33; H, 3.20; N, 11.22%); ν_{\max} 3352 (NH), 1767 (oxadiazolinone C=O), 1651 cm⁻¹ (amide C=O); δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 2.31 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.26 (2H, d, ArH, *J* 8.1 Hz), 7.60 (2H, d, ArH, *J* 8.1 Hz), 7.84 (2H, d, ArH, *J* 8.2 Hz), 8.13 (2H, d, ArH, *J* 8.2 Hz), 10.21 (1H, s, NH, D₂O exchanged). **5c** (66%), m.p. 123–125° (Found : C, 65.72; H, 4.59; N, 13.23. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₅N₃O₃ : C, 66.01; H, 4.85; N, 13.59%); ν_{\max} 3351 (NH), 1783 (oxadiazolinone C=O), 1651 cm⁻¹ (amide C=O); δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 2.25 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.36 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.41–7.67 (4H, m, ArH), 7.88 (2H, d, ArH, *J* 8.0 Hz), 8.03 (2H, d, ArH, *J* 8.0 Hz), 10.19 (1H, s, NH, D₂O exchanged). **5d** (72%), m.p. 111–114° (Found : C, 65.96; H, 4.71; N, 13.05. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₅N₃O₃ : C, 66.01; H, 4.85; N, 13.59%); ν_{\max} 3362 (NH), 1763 (oxadiazolinone C=O), 1661 cm⁻¹ (amide C=O); δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 2.29 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.39 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.16 (2H, d, ArH, *J* 8.3 Hz), 7.65 (2H, d, ArH, *J* 8.3 Hz), 7.91 (2H, d, ArH, *J* 8.6 Hz), 8.11 (2H, d, ArH, *J* 8.6 Hz), 10.21 (1H, s, NH, D₂O exchanged). **5e** (71%), m.p. 142–144° (Found : C, 57.72; H, 3.37; N, 12.38. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₂ClN₃O₃ : C, 58.18; H, 3.63; N, 12.72%); ν_{\max} 3357 (NH), 1759 (oxadiazolinone C=O), 1665 cm⁻¹ (amide C=O); δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 2.38 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.32–7.53 (4H, m, ArH), 7.90 (2H, d, ArH, *J* 8.1 Hz), 8.09 (2H, d, ArH, *J* 8.1 Hz), 10.36 (1H, s, NH, D₂O exchanged). **5f** (67%), m.p. 136–138° (Found : C,

57.84; H, 3.39; N, 12.45. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₂ClN₃O₃ : C, 58.18; H, 3.63; N, 12.72%); ν_{\max} 3363 (NH), 1764 (oxadiazolinone C=O), 1655 cm⁻¹ (amide C=O); δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 2.35 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.48 (2H, d, ArH, *J* 8.7 Hz), 7.82 (2H, d, ArH, *J* 8.7 Hz), 7.92 (2H, d, ArH, *J* 8.6 Hz), 8.12 (2H, d, ArH, *J* 8.6 Hz), 10.40 (1H, s, NH, D₂O exchanged). **5g** (70%), m.p. 150–152° (Found : C, 62.40; H, 4.37; N, 12.68. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₅N₃O₄ : C, 62.76; H, 4.61; N, 12.92%); ν_{\max} 3412 (NH), 1776 (oxadiazolinone C=O), 1661 cm⁻¹ (amide C=O); δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 2.36 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.83 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.28–7.43 (4H, m, ArH), 7.78 (2H, d, ArH, *J* 8.0 Hz), 7.95 (2H, d, ArH, *J* 8.0 Hz), 10.23 (1H, s, NH, D₂O exchanged). **5h** (73%), m.p. 114–116° (Found : C, 62.42; H, 4.38; N, 12.66. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₅N₃O₄ : C, 62.76; H, 4.61; N, 12.92%); ν_{\max} 3370 (NH), 1758 (oxadiazolinone C=O), 1665 cm⁻¹ (amide C=O); δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 2.41 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.72 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.32 (2H, d, ArH, *J* 8.1 Hz), 7.54 (2H, d, ArH, *J* 8.1 Hz), 7.89 (2H, d, ArH, *J* 8.4 Hz), 8.05 (2H, d, ArH, *J* 8.4 Hz), 10.16 (1H, s, NH, D₂O exchanged).

Acknowledgement

We thank Dr. G. S. Puranik, Retired Professor of Organic Chemistry and former Chairman, Department of Chemistry, Karnatak University, Dharwad, for encouragement and suggestions. Authors also wish to thank SIF, Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore and USIC, Karnatak University, Dharwad, for providing spectral data.

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